

Peer-reviewed academic journal

**Innovative Issues and Approaches in
Social Sciences**

IIASS VOLUME 16 (2023)

Innovative Issues and Approaches in Social Sciences

IIASS is a double blind peer review academic journal published 3 times yearly (January, May, September) covering different social sciences: political science, sociology, economy, public administration, law, management, communication science, psychology and education.

IIASS has started as a Sldip – Slovenian Association for Innovative Political Science journal and is being published by ERUDIO Center for Higher Education.

| 2

Typeset

This journal was typeset in 11 pt. Arial, Italic, Bold, and Bold Italic; the headlines were typeset in 14 pt. Arial, Bold

Abstracting and Indexing services

COBISS, International Political Science Abstracts, CSA Worldwide Political Science Abstracts, CSA Sociological Abstracts, PAIS International, DOAJ, Google scholar.

Publication Data:

ERUDIO Education Center

Innovative issues and approaches in social sciences, 2023,
vol. 16

ISSN 1855-0541

Additional information: www.iiass.com

STUDY MODEL: MEDIA DIGITIZATION AND COMMUNICATION

Mira Pavlinović¹

Summary

This paper addresses the proposal of a student education program for the digitization of media and communication and methods that explore the relationship between communication and digital forms of media. As digital technology permeates all aspects of life, traditional media and analogue culture are transformed into new and complex interrelationships. Digital cultures combine theory and reflection with practice and creation. Digital studies and digital humanities help prepare students for careers in cultural institutions such as academic libraries and museums and provide educators with tools to prepare students for the demands of the 21st century. Digital studies prepare students for every aspect of modern life requiring new literacy skills in understanding and using digital technologies. The program is designed for students who develop their careers in academic circles where education in the field of digitization of the humanities and the history of books and media are increasingly valued. The basic concept of the proposed studies is based on new media studies, internet studies, digital methods, digital sociology, data studies, digital culture, software content, digitized infrastructure studies.

Keywords: digitization, media, communication, education

Introduction

In the 21st century, the communication of information and data is of high importance for almost all professions. On the demand side, students and teachers are closing the circle around the “digital” and expressing the desire to study it, and on the supply side, the faculties and external factors require this new source of knowledge production. The proposed study model aims to present the concept of student education in the field of digitization of media and communication. The basic idea is based on the premise that digitization changes organizations’ business models, technologies,

¹ Faculty of Maritime Studies, University of Split
mira.pavlinovic@pfst.hr

and value propositions. The goal of the project is to establish digital studies to expand the social field to include digital humanities, modernize methods, and contribute to the formation of the first generation of digital visual humanities scholars. The proposed study is based on the idea of knowledge entrepreneurship. Choosing courses in digital studies provides students with the opportunity to produce digital content in a variety of formats and to critically evaluate and analyse the digital content they encounter. What is meant by digitization and data? At the individual level, these technological changes can be seen in the way recommendations for books and movies are received. To this end, data collection tools have been developed that link previously independent areas of work and life. The lack of digital studies and communication has been the motive for exploring the rich potential of digital media for critical analysis and creative discovery. The proposed program is characterized by an integrative approach to how digitization and data should be understood in their broadest sense and their interrelationships with society as a whole. The program proposed in this paper provides basic knowledge in fundamental areas such as information technology, digitization, digital transformation, communication skills, decision making, including business administration, economics, technology, innovation management, entrepreneurship, data control organization design and cognitive psychology, management, and a range of elective courses.

Digitization - a new information paradigm

Digitization affects the media and communication at two distinct levels: It initiates a fundamental change in the media system and causes the medialization of non-media systems. Digitization is a media transformation that changes traditional media and creates new media. It changes the way people use the media and how they communicate. At the same time, digitization leads to the medialization of non-media systems. Many digital technologies are becoming an integral part of systems and processes that were not previously media based. Media, communication, and information, therefore, play a key role in the structure and functional logic of many systems that were previously purely technical, economic, or social in nature. Digital transformation reflects the full integration of social and digital technologies into an organization's operations in a way that makes the most sense given the organization's goals and objectives. Digital transformation is a fundamental change in the structure and functional logic of economic, social, political, and technical systems

through the proliferation of digital technologies. The role of media in modern society is constantly expanding. In particular, the world of digital media is growing exponentially, leading to a growing demand for the latest content, modern technologies to create and distribute that content, and new content creators to produce it.

As a result of digitization, media, communication, and information are gaining a key position in the structure and functional logic of systems that have not previously been related to media and communication. Digitization thus changes the status of communication itself. Systems and processes that were previously purely technical, economic, or social in nature are acquiring an information or a communication dimension. This gives media and communication studies a new significance for understanding and shaping these systems and their operating principles¹.

The core competencies that students will gain in the proposed digital media and communication courses will also increase their employability in professions that are not solely media-oriented, as employers increasingly seek employees who are proficient in digital media technologies. Digital tools are increasingly being used in media studies, opening new vistas for research and analysis while creating new problems. These studies are aimed at students who will use digital tools in their research and provide information about applications, standards, and problems. Knowledge of digital things is becoming an ephemeral “hot commodity”, countering more optimistic claims about employability and positive impact on the business world. Digital technology and communications are constantly in flux. The proposed integrated degree in Digital Technology and Communication prepares tech-savvy students to share ideas in a world defined by digital media. The curriculum focuses on emerging technologies and teaches students to craft powerful messages, design multimedia campaigns, and build a digital identity. Given the increasing importance of digital technology in the daily lives of students, not to mention the general population, it was probably only a matter of time before the study of its relationship to society, ethics, and politics would be supported at the institutional level. Our future students will be the leading practical experts in media, communication, technology, and digitization of the future. They are the protagonists of our fast-growing Internet world, bringing with them

¹ The definition was proposed by Dr. Jörn Lengsfeld as a part of the framework of the digital age. The text was first published in Jörn Lengsfeld: Digital Era Framework.

the skills, knowledge, and critical insights needed to navigate and progress in today's algorithmic society. The world of digital media is rapidly changing and is characterized by hard work and creativity. The evolution of digital and social media has led to profound changes in cultural practices. More and more people live and work through media communication, making it even more urgent to study the relationship between culture, media, and technology. The Digital Technology and Communication program is designed to address these challenges and enable students to live and work in the digital present and future. Students will take modules that enable them to develop media production and media, and critical and analytical skills to examine the relationship between communication, digital technology, and culture. The program combines communication studies with a focus on digital innovation, practical business skills, and connections. Graduates will have skills and expertise in growing and understanding the functions and impact of the media industry, in developing skills that can be applied to a range of social functions. They will be able to collaborate with the local media industry by building their professional networks.

Fundamental preconditions for designing the content of education in the digitization of media and communications

Digital Technology and Communication are the intersection of social, communication, and computer sciences. The field provides content on a variety of digital, social, and creative media to explore connectivity as a sum of technologies, industries, and user practices. In addition to strengthening critical and analytical thinking, another fundamental premise is to equip students with the skills and knowledge necessary to work in companies, organizations, and institutions that deal with aspects of digitization and databases. Researchers in this area explore the digital communication, screen, and sound industries, focusing on imaginative, synthetic, and analytical concepts and practices across a variety of technology platforms. Topics include the exploration of complex collaborative digital environments (especially in the context of social media), the challenges of constant change in the digital arena, and the role of technology in contemporary social life. Digital Technology and Communication majors examine digital practices and cultures that shape scholarly research, creative production, and growing areas of daily life. In particular, the major aims to foster ways of thinking and activities that cross disciplinary boundaries, such as developing digital techniques to create and transfer critical theories to the level of

digital culture or exploring the possibilities and limitations of algorithmic approaches to textual evidence.

Throughout their studies, students work on real-world projects that promote their future employment by using the skills and abilities developed during their studies to contribute to industry content, research, or a real-world corporate website. Digital Technology and Communication majors address new research questions arising from digital cultures and methodologies, creatively apply digital tools and media, and develop the skills that make up 21st-century digital literacy. The widespread influence of digital media on almost all aspects of modern life requires new literacy skills to understand and use digital technologies. Digital media has shaped the needs of users and the demands of the digital media industry, providing an innovative learning experience that is directly relevant to the sector.

The proposed program aims to develop and disseminate knowledge and awareness in the field of digital technologies and their impact on the economy and people's lives, as well as to motivate the implementation of development activities in this field. The labour market will be subject to further changes in the coming years. These include the transition to project work and the expansion of remote and hybrid work systems. What can be done to prepare for the changes ahead? Leading Digital Transformation is a comprehensive, modular educational program that teaches students how to leverage exponential development technologies to transform organizations and drive growth. Digital Technology and Communication can be for any discipline - from social media and mobile phones to algorithms in self-driving cars. Digital and information technologies are a part of everyday life. Digital Media Studies is a unique major that prepares students to apply HTML, CSS, JavaScript, and creative applications from Adobe Creative Cloud and other writing tools. Some industries that employ digital media designers include creative agencies, film and video production, online companies, website development, video game companies, and marketing agencies. In a digital world, the jobs of the future will depend on digital skills. Students also have the option of choosing a course that combines courses from two or more academic disciplines into a coherent curriculum. Examples of some specific areas that have developed include digital media studies, communications, and arts management. Upon graduation, students can start careers in web design, web development, mobile app development, digital marketing, digital content creation, and interactive animation. Demand is driven by the growing popularity of mobile devices, digital marketing, and e-commerce solutions.

Today, many universities in Germany, Austria, and Switzerland offer digital study programs in many fields and disciplines. Outstanding examples include the University of Bonn, the Free University of Berlin, the Geneva School of Business, the University of RWTH Aachen, the University of Applied Sciences in Europe, the University of Kaiserslautern, the Frankfurt School of Finance and Management, the University of Lausanne, University of Bern, University of Basel, Georgia Institute of Technology, Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences, Lee Cleveland University, Roehampton University, Rochester, etc. Rochester's has a long tradition of students pursuing their goals in an environment that inspires, supports and empowers them. Rochester's unique engineering curriculum enables students to take responsibility for their programs, careers, and lives. In addition, digitization also requires appropriate skills for those involved (Rienties et al., 2013)¹. Most scholars have studied digitization primarily as either an external process (Fevolden & Tømte², 2015; Zawacki-Richter & Naidu, 2016) or an internal process (Zawacki-Richter & Latchem, 2018)³. The possibilities are endless. The programs within these studies focus on all the different digital technologies and media, their impact on people and society, and ethical and moral dilemmas that sometimes arise. Although the programs and content of the digital sciences in the aforementioned degree programs vary, they often reflect common values and methods. Communication and Digital Media was established as a study program at Aalborg University in 1985 and forms the basis for several study programs whose common denominator is the development of ICT, media, and communication⁴. Despite the strong

¹Rienties, B., Brouwer, N. & Lygo-Baker, S., 2013, 'Effects of online professional development on the beliefs and intentions of higher education teachers towards facilitating learning and technology', *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 29, pp. 122 - 31. [Crossref], [Web of Science ®], [Google Scholar]

²Cited by: Fosslund, T. , 2015. , *Digitale læringsformer i higer tdanning* (Oslo , Universitetsforlaget). [Google Scholar]

³Zawacki-Richter, O. & Latchem, C., 2018, 'Researching Four Decades of Research in Computers and Education', *Computers and Education*, 122, pp. 136 - 52. [Crossref], [Web of Science ®], [Google Scholar]

⁴Translated paper: Cathrine Edelhard Tømte, Trine Fosslund, Per Olaf Aamodt & Lise Degn (2019) *Digitization in Higher Education: Mapping Institutional Approaches to Teaching and Learning, Quality in Higher Education*, 25: 1, 98-114, DOI: 10.1080 / 13520383

trend in digital sciences towards networked and multimodal forms of knowledge, much of digital science focuses on documents and texts in a way that distinguishes the work of this field from digital research in media, information and communication sciences, and similar fields. In the high-tech, software, Internet, and data services industries today, data is at the heart of the enterprise. Innovation in software development is the key not only to increasing business agility, but also to rapidly developing and offering outstanding experiences and innovative products that deliver lasting customer satisfaction.

Research of material for modelling the study contents

The integrated digital media and communication study focuses on these skills, allowing students to solve, for example, a problem or a unique question they have identified using a digital platform. The degree prepares students to use media to make a difference in many areas of work. The integrated professional study program allows prospective students from all disciplines to explore the representation of objects, people, and content in a digital environment, develop a career-related project, and gain hands-on experience using digital tools to manipulate, visualize, and translate data and digital artifacts. Digital technologies can help improve communication, collaboration, content management, access to analytics data and social media, and employee and user experiences. Successful organizations rely on digital technologies to create workplaces that improve business cohesion. Students develop elements of design skills, master graphic design, including history and theory, and implement processes that integrate current “best practices” in research, technology, and communication. Digital media degree programs help students gain the important knowledge and skills they need in digital media, technology, and production. Digital media-focused degree programs can prepare bachelor’s graduates for careers in animation, studio production, and video game design.

Digital Technology and Communication will engage students in the discovery, analysis, and creation of digital information and media. Digital media meets the growing need for professionals ready for careers in interaction design¹.

By learning about the exciting and dynamic potential of a wide range of tools and technologies, students create innovative projects, from photo essays to web documentaries, from interactive videos to

¹ MIT Sloan Management Review and Deloitte examine executives' attitudes about what drives digital transformation

sophisticated websites, and from motion typography to 3-D visualizations. By working collaboratively with digital tools, students will tap into new sources of information and apply digital technologies in meaningful ways across a variety of fields of study. This assumption in itself justifies interest in the study, understanding, analysis, and critical thinking of society as a resource for communication and the forms and means of communication as a resource for sociability. The constant proliferation of Internet communication technologies increasingly enables people from diverse backgrounds to communicate directly and quickly with one another. By removing traditional barriers to communication, such as distance and time, these technologies can reinforce cultural rhetorical differences. This situation can be particularly problematic because both cultural and media factors can confuse the overall situational discourse. The required experience requires independent research, interdisciplinary analysis, technological skills, and the development of publicly accessible digital studies or new media projects. The proposed degree program provides students with the knowledge necessary to effectively integrate into the 21st-century digital information environment and information architecture. Courses provide marketable employment potential through the development of concrete skills in web analysis, information organization, and presentation in digital environments. Digital research facilities are information packages that students can use to organize and store their data. Currently, many different methods are used to optimize digital objects for research purposes. These methods have been applied in many scientific disciplines but differ in their architecture and approach. The field of digital studies in the world is rapidly expanding to include the research interests of social workers in the humanities, multimedia artists, and activists. This revolutionary endeavour is introducing the world to a contemporary style of thinking that has emerged directly from the culture of digitization itself. Digital Media and Communication Studies explore the creation, use, and impact of digital content and information on the humanities and art society as a whole. It brings a human perspective to issues of the digital age. These Studies allow students to develop expertise in a field that interests them while gaining technological skills. The program was proposed with the vision of combining business, law, social sciences, and technical expertise in computer and technology sciences to address the challenges of digital transformation. The flexible curriculum is tailored to the interests of individual students. Throughout the program, the students choose their specialization,

participate in online coding courses and self-study methods, complete internships, gain hands-on experience, and create a professional portfolio representing their work.

Digital Technology and Communication will enable students to expand their digital literacy; use digital media more clearly; practice basic concepts of coding; analyze, interpret, and communicate effectively; understand the meanings that can be derived from digital data; integrate and enhance the content, and practice of their education with digital tools and thinking. A graduate specialist can sharpen critical thinking skills, foster creativity, and support interdisciplinary thinking and application. Digital students will learn how to create visual content and code and deliver screen interfaces for computer applications and websites. At the intersection of these emerging fields of hardware and software, devices and users, students will engage the practical, theoretical, and ethical foundations of critical thinking in an increasingly media-driven world, with an emphasis on visual communication and information design systems, hands-on learning prepares the medium for a lifetime of experimentation and innovation. Case studies and thought-provoking insights create coherent content from a variety of fields that have helped invigorate the study of digital science and technology. Digital Technology and Communication teach students to think about how objects, words, people, and content are represented in a digital environment. Especially in today's world, where the digital dimension of information and communication is intensifying, following the recent shift in the communication paradigm: from traditional forms and means of communication to the so-called new media or the latest information and communication technologies. Skills and practical experience with digital tools for handling, visualizing, translating, and experimenting with digital information. Emphasis is placed on the efficient and ethical use and understanding of digital technologies in the digital society. The program focuses on the various digital technologies and media, their impact on people and society, and the ethical and moral dilemmas that sometimes arise. Elective courses explore media for social change, tangible computing, transmedia expression, and more, allowing students to use media to pursue their interests. All Digital Technology and Communication courses combine theory and practice in lab seminars that include hands-on instruction to help students create sophisticated media-based works. Digital Technology and Communication aim to create space for social and cultural inquiry with and about digital technology. In particular, they focus on ambitious and experimental work that explores and

critically addresses the role of digital data, methods, devices, and infrastructures in collective life, as well as the issues, challenges, and problems associated with them. In terms of content, the study is about communication, a universal but particular way of connecting people and ideas. It describes in detail the increasing and diverse uses, functions, interactions, and effects of communication in modern “world society”, emphasizing the dialectic between society and communication.

In today’s economy, there are enormous changes in technology as well as in political and economic development. The only thing that is known to be constant from day to day is change. It will never stop. That is why we are constantly developing and revising programs to adapt them to the dynamic environment of the business world. We evaluate ourselves based on our success in educating and helping students grow, and our success can only be measured by the long-term positive impact we have on the lives of our students and our community.

It is also based on the idea of combining business, law, social sciences, and technical disciplines in computer and technology sciences to address the challenges of digital transformation. The study addresses issues of power, privilege, and approaches that shape the digital world. Starting with a historical overview, students will explore topics such as digital security and privacy, digital identities, and copyright and fair use. In addition to these theoretical foundations, students will be introduced to key principles of project management and development, data analysis, visualization, and curation. By learning about and thinking critically about a variety of tools and platforms, students will develop projects that help them create a context for making informed, ethical decisions about the use of technology.

Innovative design in the 21st century requires working not only across disciplines but also across educational units that practice different ways of thinking.

Regardless of their specialized major, students will work and thrive in environments that increasingly rely on digital tools and platforms to create and share information. The Department of Digital Technology and Communication takes an interdisciplinary approach that incorporates diverse methods, frameworks, and discourses from a variety of academic fields. However, the uniqueness of the program lies in its singular focus on everything related to the phenomenon of digital technology. This includes studies of digital media, digital humanities, digital pedagogy, digital art, aesthetic practice and

design, and critical thinking about the digital technology of the future. However, separating “digital” from more traditional concepts of social science, art, and design leaves the question unanswered: what is studied in the study of digital technology? Because digital studies span so many academic disciplines, a smaller portion of digital studies attracts students from the humanities, social sciences, physical and natural sciences, and other fields. Given the increasing importance of digital technology in the daily lives of students, not to mention the general population, it was probably only a matter of time before the study of its relationship to art, society, ethics, and politics would be supported at the institutional level. They share a common interest in understanding the impact of digital technology and using digital tools to present, analyse, and preserve the human language and cultural products. Together, their work shows how digital studies span a range of human activities, from everyday speech and writing to historical documents and literary texts, and include music and art as well as mundane objects, places, and institutions.

Communication and technology are constantly evolving. The proposed integrated study of digitizing media and communication teaches tech-savvy adults and youth how to share ideas in a media-driven world. The ultimate goal of the curriculum is based on emerging technologies and teaches students to craft powerful messages, design multimedia campaigns, and build a digital identity. The emerging educational field of communication and digital studies is transforming research and learning environments and cultural preservation systems by leveraging institutional differences through collaboration that transcends traditional institutional units and hierarchies.

Conclusion

Digital Media and Communication Studies are studies that examine the relationship between communication and digital media forms by asking four questions:

- How do digital media affect the way we communicate?
- How are digital tools used to best communicate with each other?
- What is the role of visual, audio, and interactive elements of digital media and how can they be used?
- How does digitization affect the way information is accessed and understood?

The following goals should be achieved:

- Compare new and old media in terms of their form, impact, and accessibility.

- Analyse the impact of new media on social processes and news production, content, and consumption
- Demonstrate how new media impact the importance of expanding oversight and the dynamics between oversight and security.
- Discuss how new media are changing the way one thinks about the world, one's place in it, and ultimately one's identity
- Develop a persuasive, theoretically grounded argument for or against the use of new media

Digital Media and Communication Studies are a diverse and growing interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary field in which humanistic research is improving and redefining the possibilities of digital tools for research, analysis, publication, distribution, and application of scientific work¹. Students will engage in research topics of personal interest to visual culture using a variety of digital resources and analytical methods in the context of the latest theoretical discussions of the digital in the social sciences. The study program focuses on theory and practice, the Digital Technology and Communication curriculum helps students gain experience in using digital tools and develop a complex understanding of digital cultures. The curriculum covers contents such as:

- Multimedia production
- Social media
- Ethics and digital culture
- Data design and visualization
- Data literacy
- Digital identity and representation
- And others.

It combines a high-level strategy with practical tools that can be used to create digital media programs that achieve a measurable level. Students will better understand the essence of digital and social media - the clutter of platforms, applications, and devices.

The program establishes new connections across disciplinary boundaries by addressing different but overlapping areas of intellectual activity:

Digital information structures - consider and evaluate how digital archives, databases, and other digital information architectures are used and created.

¹ Michael Chui and Mark Collins · McKinsey & Company Better business: How to harness value from IoT technologies. 17th November 2021

Digital media - consideration of how digital technology-mediated communications, such as the Internet, mobile and smart devices, including digital video and audio content, as well as games and simulations produced by everyday discourse and media professionals, are used and evaluated.

Digital forms - analysis and evaluation of mechanical and aesthetic design elements in digital content, including visual, audio, interactive, and other components.

Digital practices - acquiring skills that enable the creation of expressive and strategic communication content using digital tools such as digital video and audio equipment, as well as video and audio editing software, web design, database design, information architecture, application design, computer simulation, and digital gaming.

Students of digitization of media and communication studies who meet all requirements obtain a bachelor's degree in digital studies and communications. The bachelor's degree program prepares students for careers in advertising, marketing, communications law, and more.

During their education, digital studies students study digital practices and cultures that shape professional research, creative production, and growing areas of daily life. In particular, the educational process aims to support thinking and activities that transcend disciplinary boundaries, such as developing digital techniques for creating art or music, bringing critical theory to digital cultures, or exploring the possibilities and limitations of algorithmic approaches to textual evidence.

Students in the studies of digitization of media and communication take interdisciplinary courses that make significant use of digital technologies. The following learning outcomes describe a set of goals that a student who has mastered this study should expect to work towards by fulfilling the requirements of the course:

- Develop skills for designing, creating, and sharing ideas that can be expressed through unique multimodal, procedural, and networked capabilities of digital tools.
- Explore processes of knowledge production using digital technology in researching, analysing, and conducting critical inquiry.
- Build knowledge of contemporary and historical digital cultures, including social, ethical, and philosophical issues related to technology.

- Build, promote, and maintain an active and engaged digital identity.
- Critically assess the relationship between digital media and society and analyze online platforms and content using a range of disciplinary perspectives from the humanities and/or social sciences.
- Build practical skills in using digital communication technologies with a variety of tools, including digital video and photography, mapping, and social media management.
- Understand the major theories and concepts related to digital studies and the historical context of the development of digital technologies.
- Become familiar with the methods, concepts, and tools necessary for researching and evaluating information related to digital studies.
- Think critically about how digital technologies work and their impact on society.
- Be able to create strategic communication content and self-representations using digital tools.
- Understand professional and ethical principles in the field of digital studies.
- Understand various theoretical frameworks from the history and theory of media studies.
- Learn about the aesthetic and technical design of media that you will use in critical analysis and media design.
- Acquire advanced reading, thinking, analysis, and presentation skills in the critical evaluation of texts, images, and sounds that incorporate new media.
- Conceptualize and implement media design with an emphasis on creative problem-solving techniques for digital media delivery.
- Have proficiency in writing and presentation skills and acquisition of professional skills in ethical and legal issues, teamwork, leadership, and lifelong learning.
- Prepare for careers traditionally associated with a liberal education (e.g., law, teaching, labour, public service), as well as those related to media analysis and production, including careers in the entertainment and communications industries.

Digitization of Media and Communication Studies provide students the opportunity to combine critical engagement with new forms of digital media and identities with creative and analytical practices in

the use of digital media, as well as the application of computational tools and techniques in traditional humanities fields. Although often practical or applied, Digitizing and Communicating Media are courses of study that also truly encourage and require work that is primarily critical, theoretical, or experimental in nature. Assignments are designed to balance theory with professional-level production knowledge. In all subjects, students develop strong skills in critical thinking, communication, and research. Collaboration is a hallmark of the media field, and this major requires students to work together in many courses. Students are required to demonstrate effective written and oral skills. In general, digital media and communication majors are a critical, creative response to the widespread influence of digital media on almost all aspects of modern life, especially the recognition that teaching, research, and scholarship in the humanities cannot remain isolated from the networks, platforms, and new media around us¹. This degree program will enable you to meet employer demand for employees with comprehensive and adaptable professional skills. Students will gain valuable work experience through challenging internships and build a digital portfolio of their dissertations.

During their studies, students design digital art and narration, build digital research tools for public access, and acquire computer skills that they document in their theses.

The program's curriculum provides the tools necessary to critically analyse how digitization shapes human discourse while developing a technical understanding of how digital media and content are produced and delivered to prepare students for careers in social and technological fields.

The program combines theory and practice in how digital technologies have changed the way information is shared and disseminated, how the past is understood, how people interact, and how they spend their leisure time. The digital age has changed the terms of engagement in areas as diverse as politics and culture: While it can act as a force for good, democratizing participation, production, and exchange, it can also be exploitative, introducing new forms of control and surveillance. They teach a broad range of skills in using digital tools and research methods to help students become both media researchers and active agents in a wide range of industries and cultural organizations in today's digitally mediated

¹Source: [Gannon%20University%20_%20Digital%20Media%20Communication.html](https://www.gannon.edu/digital-media-communication)

world. Undergraduate students demonstrate how digital media can help solve real-world problems. Comprehensive digital and media studies of real-world projects are designed for businesses and organizations. The Digital and Media Studies bachelor's degree program allows students to develop expertise in a field that interests them while gaining technological skills.

The flexible curriculum is tailored to the interests of individual students. Throughout the program, students choose their specialization according to their chosen fields, participate in online coding paths and course methods, complete internships, gain real-world experience, and create a professional portfolio that represents their future work. The Media Digitization and Communications student also receive extensive hands-on training in a broad range of new media using powerful software and equipment, as well as an understanding of the concepts, history, and legacy of digital media in traditional media.

The media digitization and communication student will prepare to meet the demands of a rapidly changing media environment. In this hands-on phase, he or she will develop artistic and technical skills in a range of digital media - from design principles to interactive design or motion design to filmmaking. Theoretical topics such as the cultural impact and ethical responsibilities of mass communication professionals help develop a holistic understanding of contemporary media. The STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics) 1 label is awarded to profiles that have a quantitative-technical focus and allow students to pursue an additional elective internship after graduation.

Graduates can pursue careers in multimedia design, advertising, digital content management, human resources, research, digital journalism, digital marketing, music promotion, film production, academia, archives, museums, galleries, and business consulting.

The study concept is based on close collaboration between students and faculty in teaching, team projects, and everyday work. Dedicated collaborative spaces, innovative teaching methods, and small classes allow students to develop and lead their projects. In addition, academic and non-academic mentors support students in planning and implementing new project ideas and help them build their

1 The term STEM comes from the English language and is actually an acronym composed of the initials of four areas - science, technology, engineering, and mathematics.

network. All digital studies content combines theory and practice in lab-based seminars that include hands-on instruction to help students create sophisticated media-based work. The Digital Technology and Communication major thus provides a framework for studying digital tools, culture, and practices that influence daily life and shape the way one thinks, works, plays, communicates, organizes, consumes, and learns. Digital Technology and Communication courses enable students to understand the social, political, economic, and historical context of these technologies, gain knowledge of specific methods of digital research and digital creation, and consider global networks and transnational information protocols that enable digital media.

Upon completion of the Media Digitization and Communication degree, students will be prepared for a variety of careers such as Digital Strategist, Digital media project manager, producer, or consultant, digital video expert, educational media designer, interactive media producer or consultant, mobile application designer, mobile content developer, graphic motion designer, special effects designer in post-production, media production assistant, custom skills designer, user interface designer, visual designer for print and online media, web administrator, web designer.

References:

- Cathrine Edelhard Tømte, Trine Fosslund, Per Olaf Aamodt & Lise Degn (2019) Digitization in Higher Education: Mapping Institutional Approaches to Teaching and Learning, *Quality in Higher Education*, 25: 1, 98-114, DOI: 10.1080 / 13520383
- Michael Chui and Mark Collins. McKinsey & Company. Better business: How to harness value from IoT technologies. 17th November 2021
- Fosslund, T., 2015, *Digitale læringsformer i higer tdanning* (Oslo , Universitetsforlaget). [Google Scholar]
- Rienties, B., Brouwer, N. & Lygo-Baker, S., 2013, 'Effects of online professional development on the beliefs and intentions of higher education teachers towards facilitating learning and technology', *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 29, pp. 122 - 31. [Crossref], [Web of Science ®], [Google Scholar]
- Zawackcki-Richter, O. & Latchem, C., 2018, 'Researching Four Decades of Research in Computers and Education', *Computers and Education*, 122, pp. 136 - 52. [Crossref], [Web of Science ®], [Google Scholar]